

THE PHENOMENOLOGY OF WIRE, DIELECTRICS AND FREQUENCY

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Abstract

Electrical insulation used on aircraft wiring is known to deteriorate from a number of environmental, chemical, electrical and physical processes that are detrimental in one way or another to the molecular structure of the insulation polymer. Environmental stress encountered during installation and aircraft normal operations over the life of the wire is a dynamic process and an analysis of aging wiring can easily become complicated [1-4]. *As the physical and chemical properties of the wire system deteriorate. Similar degradation takes place in the electrical properties.* Detailed examination of the chemical and physical degradation phenomenon has been well documented by various contributors to the technical journals and conference authors. However, the equivalent electrical degradation properties have not been documented or tied to system performance. This paper will discuss systems electrical properties and total systems performance as related to the Electrical Interconnect Systems (EIS) health in it's operational environment that also includes the effects of human interaction, system design and application.

Insulated copper wire has been in use for more than 100 years. Today the electrical requirements placed on copper wire by high speed electronics can exceed the wire performance capability making it a less desirable choice for certain functions than other signal distribution technologies. Copper wire performs well particularly for power distribution, DC, analog and digital signal circuits up to 300 MHz at which time non-linearities begin to be introduced. Since aircraft became computerized and electronic systems began operating well into the UHF frequencies circuit stability has become an important consideration in design and as a more commonly encountered failure mode.

Most electronic circuits that are in use everyday are inherently and mathematically

considered to have lumped circuit elements and the wires connecting them to be perfect conductors.

This assumption works well for low frequency applications. Lumped circuit elements have the desirable feature in that they introduce no phase shift into the circuit resulting from propagation delays. The amount of phase shift depends on the electrical circuit length. This shift directly affects the phase relationship between current, voltage and system stability. Above 300 MHz real world component characteristics, distributed parameters and phase/gain margins start to become critical from the standpoint of systems performance and systems stability.

At approximately 300 MHz and above ideal circuit components start to exhibit nonlinear behavior. At approximately 2 GHz the waveguide may be used. At this point computer aided design tools such as SPICE are necessary to aid in examining the electrical parameters of the wiring as a transmission line verses the combined effects of the multiple nonlinear behaviors such as: skin effect, leakage conductance, capacitive reactance, inductive reactance and electromagnetics has on the circuit. These characteristics of copper wire result in a substantial reduction in the bandwidth and linear dynamic range and introduce performance limitations at elevated frequency. Questions must be posed: Is copper wire obsolete for high frequency applications? What levels of degradation of the ELS system will begin to have effect on signal health and operational performance?

Introduction

Electrical aircraft wiring performance is known to deteriorate from a number of reasons that are related to the molecular structure of the insulation polymer, the stress of installation, environmental stress experienced during normal aircraft operation that includes the frequency of electrical system operation and maintenance events. Many of these stresses directly affect the electrical

characteristics of the electronics by initial design rules intended for systems performance making it necessary to approach the wiring issues from a systems view point. Table 1 addresses those areas where transmission line theory applies. These types of failure inherently do not pose severe risk of heat smoke and fire events, but do effect systems performance.

To locate faults in information transfer systems such as voice and computer communications a systems approach must be taken. Troubleshooting must address variation from normal operation plus the addition of a safety margin, such as providing a proactive response plan instead of a reactive response reaction [5 -7].

Training is Key

Where change is to take place, education must take place first. Today's lack of a complete understanding of complex electrical and electronic systems characteristics are a major cause of aircraft wiring problems. Rising above electrical wiring issues of today obviously requires a higher level of understanding of complex EIS including components and related avionics. Training in wire related technologies and aided by advanced computer information collection and processing is key to the electrical repairman's competency and the elimination of the majority of today's wire problems [5].

Table 1. Antidotal Causation of Electrical Faults

Percent Faults	Specifics Concerning Wiring Faults
90 %	Faults repeated aircraft to aircraft of a single type by kind & location
10%	Fault types that are seldom encountered and hard to detect
80 %	Faults that are human induced
25 % 95+%	Effectiveness of visual inspection Effectiveness of <i>advanced</i> wire inspection techniques
20 X	The number of times a fault may have to be repaired until it is correct

Defining Some of the Areas Where The Electrical Rules Change At Increasing Frequency

This paper was written to clear up some of the basic details of transmission lines and coax cables that are universal for most applications. Further information on this subject may be obtained from many reference texts. The ideal book depends on the reader's background in physics, chemistry, electrical engineering, electromagnetics, systems engineering, modern control theory, statistics and mathematics [5, 10 - 13].

Signal Wire Functionality

- Direct Current Instrumentation
- Alternating Current Analog
- Twisted pair *
- Digital bus *
- Digital, not a bus *
- Synchro, 2 & 3 phase *
- Emergency ground bus

* Systems affected by transmission line balance & special electrical rules

Figure 1. Systems That Require Analysis As A Transmission Line

A Real World Problem

From a systems engineering standpoint the avionics and aircraft manufactures need to become involved in is understanding of the operational environment their equipment must deal with. Some of the more common causes of systems failure of the EIS are human action, water intrusion, thermal and bending of the wiring and wire insulation. The following is a typical example caused by water intrusion of the polymer insulation where the normal electrical characteristics of wiring no longer follow the normal electrical rules (Figure 1, Table 1 & [5]). For high-speed circuits the cables, source and load must be matched electrically for the proper operation of the system.

The process of hydrolytic scission or water intrusion causes the polymer dielectric molecule to split substantially reducing the voltage breakdown strength of the electrical insulation that allows for an increase in the current conductance or leakage current. This alters the electrical properties of the insulated wire and produces electrical standing waves in the circuit, corrupting the data transmission and can result in system failure (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Hydrolytic Scission Alters Electrical Characteristics and Can Cause System Failure

What Is Cable Impedance and How Is It Used

The basic concept is that a conductor at RF frequency no longer behaves like a standard wire. As the length of the conductor (wire) approaches approximately 1/10 the wavelength of the signal it carries the conventional circuit analysis rules no longer apply. This is the area where cable impedance and transmission line theory start to come into play. The basic rule of transmission lines is that the source impedance must equal the load

impedance in order to achieve maximum power transfer and minimum signal reflection at the load. In the real world this generally means that the source impedance is the same as cable impedance and load impedance.

Defining Cable Impedance

The characteristic impedance of a cable is the ratio of electric field strength to the magnetic field strength for waves propagating in the cable (Volts/m / Amps/m = Ohms). Ohm's Law states that if a voltage (E) is applied to a pair of terminals and a current (I) is measured in this circuit, the following equation can be used to determine the magnitude of the impedance (Z). This relationship holds for either direct current (DC) or alternating current (AC).

$$Z = E / I$$

Characteristic Impedance is usually designated Z_0 . When the cable is carrying RF power, without standing waves, Z_0 also equals the ratio of the voltage across the line to the current flowing in the line. Thus the characteristic impedance is defined by:

$$Z_0 = E / I$$

The voltages and currents depend on the inductive reactance and capacitive reactance in the cable. Therefore the characteristic impedance can be written as:

$$Z_0 = \text{sqrt} ((R + 2 \times \text{pi} \times f \times L) + (G + j \times 2 \times \text{pi} \times f \times C))$$

Where:

- R = The series resistance of the conductor in ohms per unit length (DC resistance)
- G = The shunt conductance in mhos per unit length
- j = A symbol indicating that the term has a phase angle of +90 degrees (imaginary number)
- pi = 3.1416
- L = Cable inductance per unit length
- C = Cable capacitance per unit length
- sqrt = square root function

For materials commonly used for cable insulation, G is small enough that it can be neglected when compared with $2(3.1416) f \times C$. At low frequencies, $2 \times (3.1416) f \times L$ is so small compared with R that it can be neglected. Therefore, at low frequencies, the following equation can be used:

$$Z_o = \text{sqrt}(R + (j \times 2 \times \pi \times f \times L))$$

If the capacitance does not vary with frequency, the Z_o varies inversely with the square root of the frequency and has a phase angle that varies from -45 degrees near DC and decreases to 0 degrees as the frequency increases. Polyvinyl chloride and rubber decrease somewhat in capacitance as frequency increases, while polyethylene, polypropylene, and Teflon are stable in this respect. When f becomes large enough, the two terms containing f become so large that R and G may be neglected and the resultant equation is:

$$Z_o = \text{sqrt}((j \times 2 \times \pi \times f \times L) + (j \times 2 \times \pi \times f \times C))$$

Which can be simplified to the form:

$$Z_o = \text{sqrt}(L / C)$$

Characteristics Of Cables At High Frequencies

At high frequency the cable acts as a waveguide. The characteristic impedance for electromagnetic waves is the load the cable poses at high frequency. The high frequency usually starts at (dependent of cable) 100kHz and increases. If a sinusoidal AC signal of reasonable frequency is fed into one end of the cable, then the signal travels as an electrical wave down the cable. If the cable length is an extremely large number of wave lengths at the frequency of that AC signal, and is the ratio of AC Voltage to AC current in that traveling wave measure, then that ratio is called the characteristic impedance of the cable. In practical cables, cable geometry and the dielectric constant determine the characteristic impedance. The cable length has no effect of its characteristic impedance.

The Coaxial Cable Model

The coax is represented schematically by a series of capacitors and inductors, in the form of a ladder, the particular values unique to the coax type.

At a given frequency, if correctly chosen, that arrangement passes most of the signal; while at higher frequencies attenuates the signal (Fig. 3).

Coaxial Cable Characteristics Defines The Impedance

Wire length does not affect the coaxial cables impedance. The characteristic impedance is determined by the size and spacing of the conductors and the type of dielectric used between them. For ordinary coaxial cable used at reasonable frequency, the characteristic impedance depends on the dimensions of the inner and outer conductors, and on the characteristics of the dielectric material between the inner and outer conductors.

The following formula can be used for calculating the characteristic impedance of the coaxial cable: (formula taken from Reference Data for Radio Engineers published by Howard W. Sams & Co.).

$$\text{Impedance} = (138 + e^{(1/2)}) \times \log(D/d)$$

Where:

log = logarithm of 10

d = diameter of center conductor

D = inner diameter of cable shield

e = dielectric constant (= 1 for air)

The characteristic impedance of a coax cable is the square root of (the per unit length inductance divide by the per unit length capacitance). For coaxial cables the characteristic impedance will be typically between 20 and 150 ohms. The length of the cable makes no difference whatsoever in regard to the characteristic impedance.

If the frequency is much too high for the coaxial cable, then the wave can propagate in undesired modes (i.e., have undesired patterns of electric and magnetic fields), and causes the cable not to function properly for various reasons.

What Kind of Electrical Model is Used for Long Coaxial Cable

If you know the inductance and capacitance of a certain length of cable you can use the following electrical model for it: The transmission line electrical characteristics controls the transfer of all high-speed data transfer and computer

communications. It is desirable to understand how the electrical characteristics of this model can assist or hamper the operation of the total system

$$Z = \text{sqrt} (L / C)$$

Figure 3. Typical Transmission Line Model

Can Cable Impedance Be Measured Using A Multimeter

Cable characteristic impedance is only valid for high frequency signals. Multimeters use DC current for resistance measurements and can't measure cable impedance. It is usually best to check the cable type (usually printed on the cable) and its characteristic impedance from a handbook instead of trying to measure it.

How Is Cable Impedance Measured

A relationship exists which makes determination of Z_0 rather simple with the proper equipment. It can be shown that if, at a given frequency, the impedance of a length of cable is measured with the far end open (Z_{oc}), and the measurement is repeated with the far end shorted (Z_{sc}), the following equation may be used to determine Z_0 :

$$Z_0 = \text{sqrt} (Z_{oc} \times Z_{sc})$$

Where:

Z_{oc} = impedance of a length of cable and is measured with the far end open

Z_{sc} = impedance of a length of cable and is measured with the far end shorted

NOTE: The Z_{oc} and Z_{sc} measurements both have magnitude and phase, so the Z_0 will also have magnitude and phase. High frequency measurements of Z_0 are made by determining the velocity of propagation and capacitance of the cable or by reflectometry.

When Does Cable Impedance Effect the Signal

In order for the cable's characteristic impedance to make any difference in the way the signal passes through it, the cable must be at least a large fraction of a wavelength long for the particular frequency it is carrying.

Most wires will have a speed of travel for AC current of 60 to 70 percent of the speed of light, or about 195 million meters per second. An audio frequency of 20,000 Hz has a wavelength of 9,750 meters, so a cable would have to be four or five kilometers long before it even began to have an effect on an audio frequency. That's why the characteristic impedance of audio interconnect cables is not something most of us have anything to worry about.

Normal video signal rarely exceed 10 MHz. That's about 20 meters for a wavelength. Those frequencies are getting close to being high enough for the characteristic impedance to be a factor. High-resolution computer video signals and fast digital signals easily exceed 100 MHz so the proper impedance matching is needed even in short cable runs.

How Impedance Matching Works

First the cable should be driven by an electrical source that has an output impedance equal to the characteristic impedance of the cable, so that all of the source's output power goes into the cable, rather than being reflected from the cable's input back into the source. Secondly the electrical load of the output of the cable must have input impedance equal to the characteristic impedance of the cable. This allows all of the power to be consumed in the load rather than reflected back into the cable.

There are many exceptions to this normal driving method, but those are used for special effects. Impedance can be chosen to match for maximum power transfer at low bandwidth, or by mismatching the impedance for a flatter frequency response.

Why Is Impedance Matching Needed

If you have mismatches between the source's output impedance, the cable's characteristic

impedance, and load's input impedance, then the reflections critically depend on the length of the cable. If the cable has been distorted by crushing, kinking, or if connectors have been installed incorrectly standing waves will occur causing a loss in power reflections, with resulting power loss. Sometimes reflected power can damage the power source if its power is reflected into the cable. An anomaly that is not often considered occurs when the antenna reflects power back to the source due to an improper termination at the antenna. The return path of this reflected power will either be the inside or outside of the outer shield, depending on the path of least impedance. This means the RF can travel on the outside of the coax. The most difficult concept concerning coax is that neither XL nor XC exists at the source if the cable is terminated.

The most common reason for listing cable impedance is due to its reliable electrical characteristics. Coax is often used to carry low-level high frequency signals that are separated. Separations are very expensive in terms of signal loss, even with a perfect impedance match. Nominally, half the signal power in the transmission line is lost. A slight mismatch is also quite costly, particularly at transmitter power levels. Carefully matched carriers, like coax, are necessary to preserve signal at reduced noise.

What Effect Does The Nominal Capacitance Have On The Cable's Performance Or Transmission Capabilities

Capacitance of the cable has nothing to do with the signal if the coax is terminated. The transmitter will see absolutely no capacitance nor inductance. This transmission line characteristic is used to hide capacitance in high frequency PCB's. Engineers can design the PCB traces so that they have the proper capacitance and inductance values allowing the source to see nothing but a proper impedance.

Why Is Characteristic Impedance Important In Data Transmission

If a cable is terminated in its matching characteristic impedance there is no way of telling from the sending end that the cable is not infinitely

long – entire the signal that is fed into the cable is consumed by the cable and the load.

If the impedance is not matched, a portion of the power will be reflected back into the cable termination distorting the outbound signal. When this reflected signal format returns to the source it is again reflected and mingles with the outbound waves so that it is difficult to tell which waves are original and which are re-reflections.

The same thing happens when pulses are sent down the cable - when they encounter impedance other than the characteristic impedance of the cable, a portion of their energy is reflected back to the signal source. If the pulses encounter an open circuit or a short circuit, all of the energy is reflected except for the losses due to attenuation. For other terminations, a smaller amount of power is reflected.

This reflected energy distorts the pulse, and if the impedance of the pulse generator is not the same as the characteristic impedance of the cable, the energy will be re-reflected back down the cable, appearing as extra pulses.

Is Coaxial Cable Useful Without Impedance Matching

If the coaxial cable is very short, the cable impedance does not have much effect on the signal. Usually the best way to transmit signal through coaxial cable is to do the impedance matching, although there are some applications where the normal impedance matching on both ends is not done. In some special applications the cable might be impedance matched at only one end or intentionally mismatched at both ends. Those applications are special cases, where the cable impedance is taken into account though the combination of cable and cable terminations that produce the desired transmission characteristics for the whole system. In this kind of special application the cable is not considered as a passive transmission line, but a signal-modifying component in the circuit.

Velocity Of Propagation Ratio

The velocity of propagation ratio percentage is based on the speed of light in a vacuum. The percentage identifies the speed of the signal in the

cable compared to the speed of light in a vacuum. In coax cable, under reasonable conditions, the propagation velocity depends on the characteristics of the dielectric material.

Why Does The Signal Attenuation Tend To Increase With Increasing Frequency

This is usually due to the limited penetration of current into the inner and outer conductors (the skin effect). With increasing frequency, the current penetrates less deeply into the conductors, and thus is confined to a thinner region of metal near the surface. Therefore the attenuation, is higher. It also can be caused partly by energy loss in the dielectric material.

How To Minimize The Attenuation In Coax

For a line with fixed outer conductor diameter, and whose outer and inner conductors have the same resistivity, and assuming a dielectric is used with negligible loss (such as polyethylene or Teflon in the high-frequency range), then a minimum loss is experienced if the expression:

$$(1/d + 1) + \ln(1/d)$$

is minimizing where d is the ratio of inner conductor diameter to outer conductor inside diameter. An approximation is = 3.5911. The formula is derived in *Reference Data for Engineers* published by Howard Sams.

Note: minimum loss does not directly yield line impedance. The line impedance depends on the dielectric constant. If the line is insulated with solid polyethylene, the minimum attenuation is about 50.6 ohms or RG-58 cable that is used for antenna feeds and test equipment leads. Note that a foam-dielectric line with the same impedance and outer diameter as a solid-dielectric line will have lower loss. To get the same impedance, the foam line will have a larger inner conductor. The larger conductor has a lower RF resistance, and therefore lower loss.

Using Coaxial Cables In Applications

What happens if a 50 ohm cable video 75 ohm cable is used? If a 50 ohm cable sees a 75 ohm load

a substantial part of the signal will be reflected back to the source. Since the source is also 75 ohm, this reflected signal will substantially be reflected back to the load. Because of the delay, it will show up as a nasty ghost in the picture. Multiple ghosts like this look like ringing. Also, the reflections cause partial signal cancellations at various frequencies. Thus the ghost on the TCAS display.

Impedance Matching Between Different Impedance

If two cables with different impedance are connected together or a cable is connected to a source which has different impedance then some kind of impedance matching is needed to avoid the signal reflections in the place where the cables are connected together [7 & 8].

Conclusions and Recommendations

Where change is to take place education must take place first. Today's standard wiring practices are the major cause of aircraft wiring problems particularly where aircraft related tradesmen lacking an understanding of the wiring issues are concerned. To rise above electrical wiring issues of today obviously requires a higher level of understanding of the wiring systems and the systems wiring is connected. Training in wire related technologies and aided by advanced computer information collection and processing will greatly aid in the electrical repairman's competency and eliminate the majority of today's wire problems.

Had the TCAS system of before been designed for operation at any higher a frequency the balanced set of coax cables would have been a losing proposition. Above approximately 2 GHz fiber optics or a wave guide must be used. The coax was operating at a frequency where there was little headroom to allow for any systems variation The waveguide is simply a tube which energy is transmitted in the form of electromagnetic waves. At this time waveguides have very rarely been used on aircraft. This is a case where the rules governing communication media (wire systems) operate are transitioning from one mode to another. That is:

1) to 300 MHz (bulk components, I=E/R), 2) Coax cable and transmission line, (distributed

components and RF rules), 3) Wave guides, electromagnetics, 4) Fiber optics (virtually unlimited bandwidth and linear dynamic range) [14].

Guidelines For Wire Husbandry

- 1) Introduce concept of BIT at LRU wire communication fault detection of entire electronic subsystem end to end.
- 2) Recognize the Navy has been able to achieve an 88% reduction in wire events through improved husbandry practices.
- 3) Audit and introduce training, which supports advanced wire husbandry practices to prevent sustained wire faults from poor work practices.
- 4) Training is key to moving beyond the attitude of fit and forget.
- 5) Consider multiplexed operation and fiber optic as a communication medium as a solution for high-speed communication to reduce the faults incurred in conventional wire design practices. Recognize the severe threat to safety from arc burning of certain types of insulation such as Kapton or Aromatic polyamide. Consider replacing with wire using insulation having less safety hazards and/or different characteristics.
- 6) Focus on having an insulation system with a minimum of insulation breaks.
- 7) Where possible use the most advanced fielded test procedures and equipment in order to overcome the fact that visual inspection is only 25% effective in identifying wiring faults.
- 8) Aircraft wiring is the communication link governing the operation of the aircraft. Based on this point of view wire husbandry must be the focus in all wire mechanical trades, engineering design and wire insulation choices. Work and inspection procedures must consider the consequences of ignoring or missing a wire fault [15 – 16]

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Disclaimer

This is one of a series of papers describing potential improvement over existing practices in use today to help ensure the continued airworthiness of all aircraft. It should be considered as a possible addition to the process of wire husbandry and condition based maintenance. It is offered as a possible technical addition to the FAA's EAPAS program where applicable.